

LINGUISTIC ANALYSIS OF EUPHEMISM RELATE TO FRIENDSHIP IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGE.

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Annotation. The purpose of this article is to cover linguistic issues of translation of social euphemisms in the Uzbek language, the theoretical and practical significance of the work is that it is possible to apply the main point of view and conclusions later on the study of this topic.

Keywords: euphemism, euphemism of the Uzbek language, linguistics, social euphemism,

There are very few euphemisms in the Uzbek language studied, what area of linguistics endemism refers to, the level of language, there are certain opinions about the subject of his study, about the pictorial image it is not. Euphemism should be regarded as lexical unity, it is worth mentioning that lexicology. Descriptions of taboo and euphemism only one lesson in the textbooks "introduction to linguistics" and "Uzbek language Stylistics" included in the program in size is no more. Three main ideas about tabu and euphemism in general science it is possible to divide into groups. These are: 1-euphemism with a primitive worldview (taboo) it appears in the influence and disappears at the cultural stage of society;

Euphemisms exist as a language fact, a passive lexical Layer; 3-euphemisms are the same in time, they say that speech serves as a tool, also for style. These views 1963-1964-in the years N.Ismatullaev's " Euphemisms in the current Uzbek language" it is reflected in the candidate's dissertation on the topic. In general, this issue to the fact that in Turkology there is an object of examination from a certain point of view even though as a research object of Stylistics already has its solution it remains as a subject to be found. Facts Eufemia is now systemic without a whole as a layer of speech to learn, to manifest all his speech capacity opening, describe the functional-stylistic features, in particular to the functional style types the most important of

today's Stylistics to shed light on the relationship between and actual problems indicate that. G'. Abdurahmonov's " To The End one of the important issues facing literary critics and linguists is literature it is to open the general and private sides of speech styles with style"; the idea also emphasizes the relevance of this topic. To the study of taboos and euphemisms in the Uzbek language, the number of dedicated scientific works is limited. Who will receive general science in the case of taboos and euphemisms by many Turkic peoples, in particular, Kazakhs, it was studied by scientists of Turkmen, Altai, Azerbaijani, Uzbek and Russian linguists. Of them Aliyev, N.Ismatullaev, N.M.Jabbarov, V. B. Like every other we can pass linguists. The theoretical and practical significance of the article is that later on the same topic the main point during the study is that it is possible to apply theories and conclusions, title more in depth knowledge of the result of the work for Turkish language learners can give the opportunity. The theoretical conclusions of this work are the following: in a large scientific-monographic plan (for example, euphemism of function style types, professional speech euphemism, non-linguistic means euphemism) vs. In addition to paving the way to study, the theory of technology in general, Stylistics, language, and speech, speech culture, the art of Word application, artistic skills, the study of visual means, the issues of setting a norm, criterion, limit to them further help the scope of the study. Eufemia separately it is the basis for the formation as a sphere. Euphemism is a relatively soft expression of rude or vulgar words and phrases. Eufemism in the determination of various misconceptions, superstitions, religious beliefs the events of the surrounding world, in the name of the determination of a clearly defined thing of the result of lexical prohibitions, what caused human cynical expressions indicates its application. In other words; it is shameful to say, it is terrible to be heard, it is considered dangerous, unpleasant, something that evokes bad feelings in a person soft, gentle, pleasant, caressing, carefree, beautiful meaning-content it is said that the expressive word and phrase (euphemism) is replaced. In this work, we will examine the status of the Prohibition results of euphemisms in the case of the Turkish language. The proximity of the scope of application of euphemisms in Turkish and Uzbek especially Sonora are the words that we meet in our speech and those that we encounter in life it is manifested in euphemisms, which are suffocating to events. In this work, we deeper the euphemisms associated with the theme" Death "and the theme" disease we studied. Adil Ahmedov in his work" taboos and

euphemisms in Turkic languages methods of justification of euphemisms; "euphemistic metaphors, euphemistic metaphor, irony, euphemisms from pronouns, other forms of extremism effects deformation, 3 point, derived words, expressing the meaning of respect such concepts as" euphemisms" are analyzed. A distinctive feature of euphemisms is their constant transformation. The euphemistic words used in the language as euphemism later defined this feature losing begins to be used in its meaning and to form a new euphemism word the need arises. The term "euphemism", adopted in the languages of the whole world (German euphemisms, French euphemism, English euphemism) Greek "eupheme" (a good, original word) appeared from the core. Due to the verbal subject or environment, he or she is a person who has a habit of doing or cynicism, rude or politely can be judged by point of view. Themes of death and burial, if this phenomenon is acute (to the moment of speech correctly or with a time that is not greater than it is different), with the help of euphemisms, the ending is pronounced. For example " " giving to the Earth put" (but not bury), as well as in the speech of medical personnel: "Losing the patient – - to prevent the death of the patient, to correct the disease disorders failure, the children "go away " (die); instead of the funeral "religious services" and others. This theme and environment of euphemism is called personal possible: they are talking, conversational and into the personal life of a third person it is tied. Thus, the environments in which euphemisms are applied are as follows: 1. Diplomacy: "the principle of mutual friendship" ("eye to eye") 2. The act of domination as a punishment: instead of "prison"" take hold", "supreme judgment "instead of" death penalty". 3. State and military secrets: "processing of unusual types of weapons" (bacteriological referring to the gun) 4. Army, intelligence, police, Criminal Investigation, and some other authorities members should not work on the job, "appearance". Applicable here words and phrases with a common meaning, a concrete action at that time and applies to the case " "task", "operation", " object" - " secret it comes in the meaning of" a person who needs to be visually observed". 5. Service environment: "goods that need to grow", (deficit), in household speech and colloquial language "organize", "compose", etc. the phrase " Help to get a mole " is common. 6. The relationship between different nationalities and social group, the status of these groups: "Non-Indigenous population"; "ethnic cleansing" – in one or another district, destruction of persons of a nation that does not belong to the same authority " " danger raised groups" - addicts,

homosexuals, Phoebe. 7. In some types of professions, denoting a goal, the position of this profession applied to increase or close some defects euphemisms. "Operator of cleaning works" (previous own euphemism lost the meaning of "assimilator");" acting (performer) " - the death penalty acting person (previous quote; executioner"); instead of the milkman quot; car with a milking operator". At the first stage of the development of society, it seemed that euphemism, then it ceases to be euphemism and calls the object extreme. Example:" defected (there is a physical or mental deficiency) " the question was common, this the scientific term had to cover many different words: mind norms, norms (poor quality), unconscious – "immature", weak in mind, mad, unpleasant (naughty) - sometimes even overarching and crazy and many other examples again. Some of these words when there was a euphemism, then to the correct and solid word have become... " new tools and methods of expressing spiritual dissatisfaction quickly it loses its euphemistic meaning and is used in the right sense " "the mind is weak", "hit by the head", "the roof is gone" and so on. In addition to the time factor there is also a more social factor. The same thing in the study of accent and colloquial language it was noticed that those who carry on themselves a few Anatomy and a person turns the name of the object and action related to physiology, related to the genus how words are used in the social lexical function, is also used in emotional expressions. But some a euphemism in this social environment there are needs, demands of speeches. For example, in the dialect and colloquial language, the object, the process is an advanced lexical signifying the meaning of the Prohibition of properties there are tools. In some modern Russian conversational language speakers use the phrase "Women's summer "in combination with the phrase" summer of campers". Euphemisms perform a social jargon of specific functions. Among them the main thing-to mask the essence, sometimes with elements of humor, Play, excitement. For example, about the prison – "Academy", "resort", "dacha", hand shackles on" bracelet“, on steal” roll wash“, on " roll clean”, about the corpse "lost an eye", with drug trafficking about the which is taken through a syringe about the substance "colic“, about the drug” Greens ". Euphemism this is the meaning used in oral or written speech is neutral and the task of the word "quot; is a word that is emotional, rude or "cynical" words apply instead. Euphemism has its peculiarity. It is the linguistic essence of euphemism it is to show. For the process of euphemisms, there are the following aspects: The speaker expresses his opinion

through language and speech units. In the process basically, from the tools that directly express the meaning of concepts uses, concrete objects, reality, human activity environment, and human attitude is reflected in speech. But these are mitigations of the situation, rude does not describe, avoid using words directly, communicate the culture is important in expressing respect and others among the speakers. In our speech, only the specified subjects and units related to the environment are also it is applied. The speaker is simply rude in this or that choice of meanings not only does the vision soften the words or phrases, but also hide the original meaning, comes with masks. Subordination to the terms of context and speech in the application of euphemisms: defect the tougher the social control of the situation, the harder the euphemisms come the probability of output is so strong that; and, control of the speech situation weakness, as well as an unusually high level of speech, (family members and friends in communication with,) euphemisms prefer either “open(direct)” meaning or difemizm. Euphemisms as a euphemism in some conditions if assessed, it is assessed differently in another situation. . In the use of euphemism in the social and personal relationships of the speaker, the most important purpose of the conversation is from the continuing unpleasant or mutual conflict escape is an attempt not to cause discomfort in the interlocutor. Applied for camouflage in a relatively specific, social sense there are euphemisms.

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